

TRENDS IN THE VERTICAL OZONE DISTRIBUTION OVER THE FARADAY/VERNADSKY ANTARCTIC STATION FROM 1957 TO 2023

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Observations of the vertical distribution of ozone over the Faraday/Vernadsky station have been conducted from October 1957 to the present. This report analyzes variations and trends in ozone concentrations at different altitudes over almost 70 years. Conventionally, this observation period is divided into several parts: before the ozone hole detection (1957–1980) and the period of ozone depletion (1980–2023). From 1957 to 1973, observations based on data from the British Antarctic Survey were considered [1]. Data from 1973 onward is the original series of ozone observations over the Faraday/Vernadsky Antarctic station, which have been processed [2]. This unique series of observations spans the period before and during the ozone hole. Observations were carried out using the Umkehr method on a Dobson spectrophotometer. The UMK92 ozone profile retrieval algorithm was used to calculate the profiles.

In the period before the ozone hole, from 1957 to 1980, the partial ozone column at the maximum of the ozone profiles varied from 50 DU/layer to 100 DU/layer, with the maximum height in the ozone profile of 19–23 km (altitude level 4). During this period, the ozone hole was not recorded. At altitudes of 23–28 km and 28–33 km, there is a tendency to increase the amount of ozone by 0.86 DU/year and 0.48 DU/year, respectively. A decrease in ozone is observed at altitudes of 10–14 km at a rate of –0.58 DU/year.

Based on 50 years of observations (1980–2023), the trends of ozone profiles in the atmosphere above the Faraday/Vernadsky station, from the time until the appearance of the ozone hole, at heights corresponding to the tropopause, stratopause, and the level of the highest ozone concentration, were plotted and analyzed. Slope indices for two data cases were calculated: for the total period of observation and for the observation period excluding data from the Antarctic spring months (September–November). No significant difference was found between the coefficients obtained for these cases.

1. Farman, J.C., & Hamilton, R.A. (1975). *Measurements of atmospheric ozone at the Argentine Islands and Halley Bay, 1957-72*. Cambridge, British Antarctic Survey.

2. *British Antarctic Survey, Meteorology and Ozone Monitoring, Antarctic ozone*. Available online: <https://legacy.bas.ac.uk/met/jds/ozone/>, (accessed 21 February 2025).